

Evaluation of White Button Mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) Feed on Haemato Biochemical and Gut Health of Rohu (*Labeo rohita*)

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Abstract: The primary aim of this study was to determine the impact of White Button Mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) on the gut microbiota, hematobiochemical parameters of Rohu (*Labeo rohita*). White Button Mushroom (WBM) has immunostimulatory and hematological benefits therefore, an experiment was performed using WBM to improve gut health and blood profile of Rohu. Fish were kept for 8 weeks in two groups: a control group (given commercial feed) and an experimental group (given WBM powder diet). Each group contained 20 fingerlings. Hematological parameters were assessed, and the results revealed, the mean RBC count in the treated group (T₁) was $1.30 \times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$, significantly higher than the control group (T₀), which had a mean of $0.27 \times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$; similarly mean Hb count in (T₁) was higher than (T₀). Mean WBCs counts in (T₀) was significantly lower than (T₁) counts. Hematocrit (Hct) and Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) were also high in experimental group indicating enhanced immune response in Rohu. Bacterial colonies count of (T₁) cultured on nutrient agar was 234.5×10^6 CFU, significantly higher than (T₀) counts, which were 94.7×10^6 CFU, similarly CFU counts of WBM fed group were higher in tryptic soy agar and Eosin methylene blue. This supports the potential of mushroom-based diets as natural immunostimulants in aquaculture.

Keywords: *Agaricus bisporus*, aquaculture, fish gut microbiota, hematological parameters, immunostimulant, White Button Mushroom

INTRODUCTION

The evaluation of White Button Mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) feed on gut microbiota and hematobiochemical parameters of *Labeo rohita* (Rohu) presents a novel approach in sustainable aquaculture nutrition. This study investigates how mushroom-based dietary inclusion influences the gut health and blood profile of Rohu under controlled experimental conditions. Aquaculture is the fastest-growing food production sector, now providing over 50% of global fish supply (Beveridge et al., 2015). To sustain this growth, optimizing fish nutrition is essential for ensuring growth, survival, and

health. Therefore, aquaculture research focuses on developing cost-effective, nutrient-rich feeds without synthetic additives (Tocher et al., 2010). Synthetic additives have several negative impacts, such as antibiotic resistance on fish culture therefore, various natural feed additives have been applied such as Mushrooms for their minimum environmental impacts and ability to improve gut health and boost immunity in aquaculture species (Van Doan et al., 2019). Among these Mushrooms, *Agaricus bisporus* known as White Button mushroom (WBM) holds a vital position because of its nutritional composition that includes all essential nutrients, carbohydrates, dietary fiber, fats, vitamins (Riboflavin), and natural bioactive compounds like β -glucans and antioxidants that may enhance immune function and improve gut microbiota (Liu et al., 2013; Hoseinifar et al., 2019). Mushrooms are known for their medicinal properties, offering antibacterial and antifungal benefits (Harikrishnan et al., 2018). Available literatures showed that dietary WBM could be an antibiotic alternative to promote growth (Amiri et al., 2018), improve antioxidant capacity and regulate immune function in several fish specie (Hoseinifar et al., 2019). However, no previous research has been conducted regarding the effect of dietary WBM supplementation on hematology and gut health of Rohu.

Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) is a major fish specie in aquaculture research due to its fast growth and high nutritional value because it contains protein, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins B12 and D, and minerals like calcium, phosphorus, and iron and has also high consumer preference (Sarma et al., 2020). Enhancing Rohu's health through natural feed in polyculture systems supports sustainable aquaculture (Jena et al., 2007). Fish hematology can be used as a tool to determine the health profile of fish (Fazio et al., 2018). Furthermore, research has shown that the gut microbiota of Rohu can be modulated through the use of probiotics and prebiotics, which can help to improve its growth, immunity, and disease resistance. However, very limited work was carried out on button mushroom (Rajani et al., 2023). For the first time in aquaculture, it was used by Harikrishnan et al. (2018) and conclude that 5% and 10% of its extract can be used to improve *Clarias gariepinus* hematology and enhance its immunity against *Flavobacterium columnare*. Current study focuses to evaluate the effect of White Button Mushroom on hematobiochemical and gut health of Rohu which can in turn increase the output of aquaculture.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiment was conducted at Fish Microbiology Laboratory, located at Fish Farm, Department of Zoology, Wildlife and Fisheries, University of Agriculture Faisalabad. Local Ethics Committee principles have been followed with ethical approval number 2249-12 dated 11/02/2025, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad.

Feed Formulation

White button mushroom powder was made from fresh healthy mushrooms purchased through market. The fresh water mushrooms were washed to get rid of any dirt and impurities. Next, the mushrooms were cut down into thin, uniform slices to ensure they dried evenly. A food dehydrator/oven was utilized for drying mushrooms at temperatures between 50–60°C for 6–8 hours (or for 2–3 days if air-dried them) until they were completely dry and brittle. After they were dried, the mushroom slices were blended in a blender (or spice grinder) to create a fine powder and shifted it to eliminate any larger particles. Finally mushroom powder was stored in an airtight container (Habib et al., 2021). The prepared feed was then added to the experimental aquarium at final concentration of 2% based on their body weight

Fish Sampling and Experimental Design

Rohu, ranging between 1.5g-7g were caught using netting from the freshwater earthen pond at the University of Agriculture Faisalabad. A total of 80 Rohu fingerlings were collected for experimental and control groups. All fish were healthy but to avoid any infection the fishes were treated with 0.2% of KMnO₄ solution and acclimatized for a period of 48 hours according to the method of Habib et al. (2021) and then divided into two groups: Control group fed with commercial feed, and the experimental group fed with 2% WBM powder diet. The mean water quality parameters, including temperature 24±2°C, DO, salinity, and pH, were measured by HANNAI-9146 and HANNA HI-8424, respectively (Dawood et al., 2020).

Blood Sampling and Gut Health Parameters

Following the experimental diet, 0.4 cc of blood samples was taken from the caudal vein of ten healthy, randomly chosen fish using a sterile syringe and a 22-gauge needle. The samples were then kept at 4°C in plastic tubes with EDTA (an anticoagulant) before being sent to the lab for prompt analysis (Torrecillas et al., 2011). Hemoglobin concentration (Hb) and white blood cell (WBC), and red blood cell (RBC) counts were performed in accordance with standard protocol (Houston, 1990). Differential WBC and RBC counts were conducted Giemsa-stained blood smears. While the hemoglobin (Hb)

concentration was measured using a spectrophotometer (Model RA 1000, Technicon Corporation, USA) at 540 nm using the Blaxhall and Daisley (1973) method, the packed cell volume (PCV, %) was calculated using the micro hematocrit method (Dawood et al., 2020).

intestinal samples using sterile tools post-pithing, and storing them in 0.5 ml of 0.9% NaCl saline in Eppendorf tubes at 4°C according to the method of Sarma et al. (2020). Nutrient agar was prepared by dissolving 18.75 g in 250 ml distilled water, autoclaving at 121°C for 20 min, and pouring into sterile Petri dishes for microbial culture by following the method of Atlas *et al.* (2010). After pouring nutrient agar into sterile Petri plates and allowing it to solidify, the intestinal suspensions were inoculated and incubated at 28-30°C for 24-48 hours to obtain visible bacterial colonies. Distinct colonies were carefully examined for their morphological characteristics, such as size, color, margin, and elevation.

Representative colonies were picked and subjected to Gram staining, followed by microscopic observation to determine Gram reaction (positive or negative), bacterial shape (cocci, bacilli, spirilla), and cellular arrangement (single, pairs, chains, or clusters). For further identification, fresh and pure colonies (not the stained samples) were selected from agar plates and inoculated into different biochemical media, including TSI agar, citrate agar, SIM medium, and urease test, to assess their metabolic traits. The combined results of colony morphology, microscopic examination, and biochemical profiling were then compared with standard references to identify the bacterial species.

Statistical analysis

Blood test's data and Gut microbial data was subjected to statistical analysis at the end of trial. T-test was performed to compare the mean of two variables. The statistical analysis was carried out using MS Excel (Software), and the significance level was adjusted at $\alpha = 0.05$.

RESULT

Gut health

Total bacterial count CFU and total microbiological content of intestine sample of rohu (*Labeo rohita*) cultured on three culturing medias viz., nutrient agar, tryptic soy agar, and eosin methylene blue. Gut samples colony-forming unit (CFU) values showed that a range of microbial communities cultivated on three distinct Agar media. The treatment's

Mean±SD values revealed a considerable difference between control and experiment group in terms of bacterial counts. Gut's bacterial count was significantly greater in experimental group (P<0.05) than in control group (Table 1).

Table 1. Total Viable Count of To and T1 on Different Media

Media	T ₀ -CFU	T ₁ -CFU	P-Value	Significance/NS
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD		
Nutrient Agar	94.7±14.80	234.5±37.21	0.0001**	Significant
Tryptic soy Agar	75.4±24.5	171.9±50.33	0.0001**	Significant
Eosine Methylene Blue	107.2±14.80	215.2±37.21	0.0001**	Significant

Bacterial Species Identification

Bacterial species isolated from the gut of Rohu fingerlings revealed a distinct difference between control and WBM-fed groups (Table 2). The experimental group showed a higher prevalence of beneficial bacteria such as *Bacillus subtilis* and *Enterococcus faecalis*, while pathogenic bacteria, including *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, were markedly reduced compared to the control group. These findings suggest that supplementation of WBM feed promoted probiotic bacterial growth, suppressed potential pathogens, and thus contributed to improved gut health, reflecting the success of the feeding trial.

Table 2. Bacterial Species Isolated From Gut of Rohu in Control (To) and Experimental Group (T₁)

Identified species	Gram reaction	Morphology	Control tank(T ₀) Result	Experimental tank(T ₁) Result	Role in fish health
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Gram+	Rods	Present (moderate growth)	Abundant growth	Probiotic, enhances digestion and immunity
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	Gram -	Rods	High growth	Reduced growth	Opportunistic pathogen causing gut infections

<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	Gram +	Cocci in chain	Low presence	Moderate growth	Probiotics, improves gut microbiota balance
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Gram -	Rods	Low growth	Moderate growth	Some strains are beneficial, improve nutrients cycling
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Gram +	Cocci in clusters	Moderate growth	Low present	Opportunistic pathogen, harmful in excess

Haemato Biochemical Parameters

Haematological parameters such as RBCs, WBCs, Mean cell Hemoglobin, Hematocrit, Mean cell volume were assessed at the end of trial, and data were analyzed statistically by using T-test on MS Excel. Results show significant differences in each parameter between control and experimental group. The results showed an elevation in RBCs, WBCs, Hb, and MCH level of fish cultivated in the WBM-fed group. The results are represented in graph below. These findings suggest that White Button Mushroom (WBM) supplementation has a positive influence on the haematological profile of *Labeo rohita*. Increased red blood cell counts and hemoglobin levels indicate better oxygen-carrying capacity of blood, which ultimately supports enhanced metabolism and growth performance

Similarly, the rise in white blood cell count reflects a strengthened immune response, highlighting the immunostimulatory effect of mushroom-based feed. Elevated hematocrit and mean cell volume further support the evidence of improved erythropoiesis and better physiological status in experimental fish. Such improvements in blood parameters are consistent with previous studies reporting the bioactive role of mushrooms, especially due to their polysaccharides, antioxidants, and immunomodulatory compounds. The enhancement of haematological indices is also an indirect indication of reduced stress and improved gut microbiota balance in the WBM-fed group, as healthy microbial flora contributes to nutrient absorption and overall health,

Thus, the haemato-biochemical outcomes not only confirm the nutritional benefits of WBM feed but also validate its importance in Aquaculture industry.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of Hb counts of Rohu in To and T₁

Figure 2. Graphical representation of RBCs counts of Rohu in To and T₁

Figure 3. Graphical representation of WBCs counts of Rohu in To and T₁

Figure 4. Graphical representation of MCH counts of Rohu in T₀ and T₁.

Table 3. Total counts of different hematological parameters of Rohu

Parameter	T ₀	T ₁	P-Value	Significance/NS
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD		
RBC (10 ⁶ /μl)	0.27±0.14	1.307±0.27	0.0001**	Significant
Hb (g/dL)	1.34±0.29	4.483 ±0.53	0.0001**	Significant
HCT (g/dL)	14.501±3.01	39.235±5.55	0.0001**	Significant
MCV (fL)	97.241±3.61	106.05±3.77	0.0001**	Significant
MCH	17.06±2.97	35.08±5.03	0.0001**	Significant
MCHC (g/dL)	26.93±0.912	39.176±0.89	0.0001**	Significant
WBC (10 ³ /μl)	26.7±4.98	64.1±15.31	0.0001**	Significant

The results indicated the mean RBC count in the treated group (T₁) was $1.30 \times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$, significantly higher than the control group (T₀), which had a mean of $0.27 \times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$, similarly mean Hb count in (T₁) is 4.48g/dL, which is higher as compare to (T₀) which was 1.34g/dL. Mean WBCs counts in (T₀) was significantly lower then (T₁) counts. Hematocrit (Hct) and Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) were also high in experimental group indicating enhanced immune response in Rohu. Bacterial colonies count of (T₁) cultured on nutrient agar was 234.5×10^6 CFU, significantly higher then (T₀) counts, which were 94.7×10^6 CFU, similarly CFU counts of WBM fed group were higher in tryptic soy agar and Eosin methylene blue.

DISCUSSION

This study assessed how the food additive White Button Mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) affected *Labeo rohita*'s gut microbiota and hematological profile. The results show that adding WBM significantly boosted fish health, as seen by higher bacterial colony counts and improved blood parameters. The experimental group's gut microbial numbers, as measured by CFU on TSA, NA, and EMB medium, were noticeably greater. This implies that WBM stimulates the growth of gut microbes, possibly as a result of the prebiotic properties of its fiber and polysaccharide content. The observed hematological improvements are further supported by the critical function that a healthy gut flora plays in nutrition absorption and disease resistance.

Red and white blood cell counts, hemoglobin concentration, hematocrit, MCV, and MCHC were all significantly higher in the mushroom-fed group than in the control group, according to hematological study. The elevated levels of RBCs and Hb suggest enhanced oxygen-carrying capacity. These enhancements point to improved erythropoiesis, increased oxygen delivery, and more robust immunological responses. Particularly, the increase in WBC count suggests immune-stimulation, most likely brought on by bioactive substances in WBM like β -glucans, which are known to strengthen innate immunity. These results are in line with other research showing that fish given natural supplements like spirulina or herbal extracts have better hematological condition.

It's interesting to observe that while growth performance is emphasized in many mushroom research, the current paper emphasizes improvements in gut health and immunity, which are equally important for sustainable aquaculture. Higher survival rates, less susceptibility to disease, and increased production are all closely correlated with improved haematological and microbiological characteristics. This is in line with the rising demand for functional feeds that enhance animal comfort and farm profitability in addition to meeting nutritional needs.

The enhanced health condition of *L. rohita* was probably influenced by the biological activity of mushrooms, particularly their immunomodulatory and antioxidant qualities. These findings are consistent with other studies using mushroom-based feed additives. Aminzadeh *et al.* (2024) reported significant improvement in hematological and immunological parameters in *Huso huso* fed with *Agaricus bisporus*. Zakariaei *et al.* (2022) showed that button mushroom and probiotics synergistically enhanced gut microbial composition and immune gene expression in zebrafish. White button mushroom (*A. bisporus*) powder in fish feed improve both hematological indices and gut

microbial health. This dual benefit positions WBM as a sustainable, natural immunostimulant and feed additive for the freshwater aquaculture system.

Overall, the study's findings provide evidence to the idea that supplementing fish with White Button Mushrooms enhances their immunity, haematology, and gut microbial balance by means of its bioactive ingredients, especially β -glucans. Because of these two positive aspects, WBM is a viable option for a functional feed additive in freshwater aquaculture, potentially replacing or lowering the need for antibiotics. These results support the inclusion of additives derived from mushrooms in commercial aquaculture feeds and further the global trend towards sustainable and health-conscious aquaculture methods.

However, it is important to recognize that the optimal inclusion level of WBM was not varied in this study. Future studies could explore graded levels of WBM to determine the Dosage-dependent effect.

CONCLUSION

The current study concludes that dietary supplementation of White Button Mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) at 2% inclusion level significantly improved the gut microbiota and hematological parameters of *Labeo rohita*. Enhanced RBCs, WBCs Counts, hemoglobin level, and microbial colony counts indicate that WBM positively influenced fish immunity, digestion, and overall health. These findings support the use of WBM as a functional feed additive to promote fish welfare and reduce dependence on synthetic antibiotics in Aquaculture. Given the natural immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties of Mushrooms, they offer a promising alternative for sustainable aquaculture practices. The outcome of this research opens new perspectives on incorporating edible mushroom in aquafeeds, and further investigation are recommended to explore dosage optimization and underlying molecular mechanism.

Conflict of interest

There are no reported conflicts of interest by the authors.

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